

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

CIED - PHYSIOLOGICAL PACING

LVSP and LBBP Result in Similar or Improved LV Synchrony and Hemodynamics Compared to BVP

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND The effect of left ventricular septal myocardial pacing (LVSP) and left bundle branch pacing (LBBP) on ventricular synchrony and left ventricular (LV) hemodynamic status is poorly understood.

OBJECTIVES The aim of this study was to investigate the impact of LVSP and LBBP vs biventricular pacing (BVP) on ventricular electrical synchrony and hemodynamic status in cardiac resynchronization therapy patients.

METHODS In cardiac resynchronization therapy candidates with LV conduction disease, ventricular synchrony was assessed by measuring QRS duration (QRSd) and using ultra-high-frequency electrocardiography. LV electrical dyssynchrony was assessed as the difference between the first activation in leads V₁ to V₈ to the last from leads V₄ to V₈. LV hemodynamic status was estimated using invasive systolic blood pressure measurement during multiple transitions between LBBP, LVSP, and BVP.

RESULTS A total of 35 patients with a mean LV ejection fraction of 29% and a mean QRSd of 168 ± 24 ms were included. Thirteen had ischemic cardiomyopathy. QRSd during BVP, LVSP, and LBBP was the same, but LBBP provided shorter LV electrical dyssynchrony than BVP (−10 ms; 95% CI: −16 to −4 ms; *P* = 0.001); the difference between LVSP and BVP was not significant (−5 ms; 95% CI: −12 to 1 ms; *P* = 0.10). LBBP was associated with higher systolic blood pressure than BVP (4%; 95% CI: 2%-5%; *P* < 0.001), whereas LVSP was not (1%; 95% CI: 0%-2%; *P* = 0.10). Hemodynamic differences during LBBP and LVSP vs BVP were more pronounced in nonischemic than ischemic patients.

CONCLUSIONS Ultra-high-frequency electrocardiography allowed the documentation of differences in LV synchrony between LBBP, LVSP, and BVP, which were not observed by measuring QRSd. LVSP provided the same LV synchrony and hemodynamic status as BVP, while LBBP was better than BVP in both. (JACC Clin Electrophysiol 2024;10:1722-1732)
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Because biventricular pacing (BVP) does not fully restore physiological ventricular activations in candidates for cardiac resynchronization therapy (CRT), other treatment methods are being explored. Direct left bundle branch pacing (LBBP) and left ventricular septal myocardial pacing (LVSP) are new alternatives to BVP.

It has been observed that LBBP delivers greater improvements in left ventricular (LV) hemodynamic and LV ejection fraction in patients with predominantly nonischemic cardiomyopathy.^{1,2} It was also shown that endocardial LVSP performed using an electrophysiological catheter led to a similar dP/dt_{max} as BVP.³ However, the acute hemodynamic effect of LVSP using a transeptal pacing lead deployment is unknown. The hemodynamic outcomes of LBBP and LVSP vs BVP in the CRT population with both ischemic and nonischemic cardiomyopathy have not been previously investigated.

Ultra-high-frequency (UHF) electrocardiography (ECG) is a noninvasive tool that can visualize ventricular activation sequences.⁴ On UHF ECG, ventricular dyssynchrony is calculated by measuring the time delays between the activation of ventricular segments under chest leads V_1 to V_8 . The impact of various types of pacing on ventricular synchrony has been studied using UHF ECG in the past few years.⁵⁻⁸ However, the association between ventricular dyssynchrony on UHF ECG and the acute hemodynamic response during different pacing modes in CRT patients is unclear.

The aim of this study was to compare acute hemodynamic and electrical responses to LVSP and LBBP vs BVP in CRT candidates and to investigate how UHF ECG reflects the associated hemodynamic changes.

METHODS

PATIENT POPULATION. This prospective study included patients with symptomatic heart failure and indications for CRT. The study was conducted at Faculty Hospital Kralovske Vinohrady, and the Institute of Clinical and Experimental Medicine in Prague. The ethics committees of both institutions approved the project, and all patients provided written informed consent. The inclusion criteria were :1) symptomatic heart failure with LV ejection fraction $\leq 40\%$; 2) spontaneous rhythm with a non-right bundle branch block configuration and QRS duration (QRSd) ≥ 130 ms; and 3) sinus rhythm during the implantation procedure. All included patients underwent coronary angiography before device implantation. The etiology of heart failure was

considered to be ischemic if a patient had significant coronary artery disease and previous revascularization or significant coronary artery stenosis ($>70\%$) in patients without previous interventions. The rest were classified as patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy.

IMPLANTATION PROCEDURE. After left subclavian access was secured, the shock lead was fixed in the apicoseptal area of the right ventricle. Then, the coronary sinus (CS) was cannulated, and a pacing lead was placed, preferably in the middle or basal region of the lateral, posterolateral, or anterolateral branch of the CS. BVP was delivered using the electrode with the longest value of the distance from the beginning of the QRS complex to the maximum negative derivative of unipolar electrogram of the CS lead electrode simultaneously with pacing from the shock lead. Next, a Select Secure 3830 pacing lead delivered through a

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

- BVP** = biventricular pacing
- CRT** = cardiac resynchronization therapy
- CS** = coronary sinus
- ECG** = electrocardiography
- LBB** = left bundle branch
- LBBB** = left bundle branch block
- LBBP** = left bundle branch pacing
- LV** = left ventricle/ventricular
- LVSP** = left ventricular septal myocardial pacing
- QRSd** = QRS duration
- RVASP** = right ventricular apicoseptal pacing
- UHF** = ultra-high-frequency

FIGURE 2 Differences in Ventricular Dyssynchrony During Studied Ventricular Captures

(A) Local activations in leads V_1 to V_8 (the first activated segment was placed at 0 ms) on the left and mean difference between biventricular pacing (BVP) and left bundle branch pacing (LBBP) on the right. (B) Local depolarization durations in leads V_1 to V_8 on the left and mean difference between BVP and LBBP on the right. (C) QRS duration (QRSd), (D) e-DYS, (E) lv-DYS among right ventricular apicoseptal pacing (RVASP), BVP, LBBP, and left ventricular septal myocardial pacing (LVSP). All values are presented as mean \pm 95% CI. Other abbreviations as in Figure 1.

C315HIS fixed-curve sheath (both from Medtronic) was placed in the right septum, 1.5 to 2.0 cm below the superior aspect of the tricuspid valve, which was visualized using a contrast injection. The lead was screwed into the interventricular septum until fixation beats with late r/R configurations in lead V_1 were observed, at which point lead progression was stopped. Next, decremental output pacing was immediately performed to identify left bundle branch (LBB) capture.

LBB capture was confirmed if nonselective LBB capture changed to: 1) selective LBB capture (ie, the QRS complex configuration in lead V_1 changed from qR to rSR, lead V_1 R-wave peak time was prolonged while lead V_6 R-wave peak time remained the same [± 10 ms], and a discrete ventricular electrogram signal appeared); or 2) myocardial capture of the left septum (ie, occurrence of lead V_6 R-wave peak time

beat-to-beat prolongation >10 ms with a reduction in pacing output and the r/R in lead V_1 decreased in amplitude or changed to an rs, RS, or QS configuration).⁹

LVSP was performed from locations where LBB capture was not identified, with pacing outputs up to 10 V at 0.5 ms. In some patients, LVSP was confirmed only by deep septal lead deployment and paced QRS complexes with a late r/R in lead V_1 and unchanged lead V_6 and lead V_1 R-wave peak time during pacing from 10 V at 0.5 ms to loss of capture.⁶ In other patients, in addition, LVSP was also confirmed by achieving nonselective LBBP at a different pacing location during the procedure. The depth of the septal lead position was confirmed using contrast right ventricular septography.

During the implantation procedure, a concentrated effort was made to achieve at least 2 of the 3 CRT

methods that permit direct comparison of either LBBP or LVSP vs BVP. After finishing the hemodynamic protocol, the atrial lead was placed in the right atrium, and either LVSP/LBBP or BVP was retained on the basis of the pacing parameters and observed differences in systolic blood pressure.

UHF ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHIC DATA ACQUISITION AND ANALYSIS OF OTHER MEASURED PARAMETERS. A ventricular dyssynchrony imaging monitor (ISI Brno, Cardion) was used to record and analyze the 5-kHz, 14-lead electrocardiographic signals with 3-nV resolution and a frequency range of 1.5 kHz. Standard positions for chest leads V_1 to V_8 were used. UHF electrocardiographic data for all tested capture types were collected during 5 minutes of VVI pacing at 100 to 110 beats/min. Signal processing and UHF electrocardiographic map construction are described elsewhere⁴ and were the same as in previous reports.⁵⁻⁷

Global ventricular electrical dyssynchrony was calculated as the difference between the first and last activations on UHF electrocardiographic maps. Positive global ventricular electrical dyssynchrony indicates a right-to-left activation pattern, and negative global ventricular electrical dyssynchrony indicates a left-to-right activation pattern. To quantify LV electrical dyssynchrony, the time delay from the first activation in leads V_1 to V_8 to the latest activation in leads V_4 to V_8 was measured (Figure 1). Local depolarization durations under leads V_1 to V_8 were computed as the UHF QRSd at 50% of its amplitude. During hemodynamic studies and UHF electrocardiographic data acquisition, BVP with a VV delay of 0 ms was used, and nonselective LBBP was the only type of LBBP used.

ACUTE HEMODYNAMIC RESPONSE. The acute hemodynamic response was measured using a high-

precision hemodynamic protocol,¹⁰ which has been shown to accurately reflect changes in cardiac function and to be highly reproducible, with a good signal-to-noise ratio. Beat-by-beat blood pressure was measured invasively from the radial or femoral artery. Pressure signals were acquired using a LAB-SYSTEM PRO (Boston Scientific) or Prucka CardioLab (GE Healthcare) with simultaneous electrocardiographic recordings. The measurements were analyzed using customized software in MATLAB (The MathWorks), and the systolic blood pressure for each beat was calculated. Pacing was done using a heart rate that was 10 to 15 beats greater than the spontaneous rhythm to avoid interruptions. Each pacing setting was compared with reference pacing, and at least 8 alternations were evaluated between each tested pacing setting and reference pacing. Two reference pacing types were used. The first reference was right ventricular apicoseptal pacing (RVASP), and all CRT

pacing types (ie, LBBP, LVSP, and BVP) available during the implantation procedure were compared with it. The second reference pacing type was BVP, which was directly compared with LBBP or LVSP (or both), depending on availability. Data from 8 beats before and 8 beats after each transition were recorded and processed. If premature ventricular beats or fused QRS complexes were detected within these 16 beats, the data were excluded from the analysis, and additional data were acquired. The order of tested pacing settings and alternations were chosen randomly for each patient.

ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS. Global QRSD and paced lead V₆ R-wave peak time were measured using an automated electrocardiographic algorithm. QRSD was measured from the earliest to the last deflection in any of the 12 leads during spontaneous rhythms and from the pacing artifact during paced rhythms. The paced lead V₆ R-wave peak time during

LVSP and LBBP was measured from the pacing artifact to the maximum positive QRS amplitude in lead V_6 . The injury current amplitude was measured manually immediately after lead deployment in millivolts on the electrogram channel with high- and low-pass filtering of 0.5 and 500 Hz, respectively. LBB block (LBBB) was defined using the Strauss criteria. During the procedure, 2 to 3 mL contrast agent was injected through a C315 HIS sheath in the left anterior oblique projection; lead depth in the septum, for all pacing locations, was measured using an xViewer (Vidis).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS. Exploratory data analysis was performed for all parameters. Unpaired continuous and categorical variable comparisons were made using the unpaired Student's *t*-test and chi-square test. Paired and repeated-measurement comparisons were made using a linear mixed-effect model and the Tukey multiple-comparison test. The results of these models are presented as mean (95% CI); comparisons

are presented as mean differences with 95% CIs and *P* values (Figures 2 to 5, Supplemental Figure 1). Relative differences in systolic blood pressure between specific ventricular capture types are presented as percentages. *P* values <0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance. RStudio version 1.2.1335 with R version 3.6.1 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing) was used to perform the statistical analyses. The linear mixed-effect model was calculated using lme4 version 1.1-21. All values are shown as means with 95% CIs if not specified otherwise.

RESULTS

Our study included 35 patients (24 men), with a mean age of 68 ± 8 years and an average LV ejection fraction of $29\% \pm 6\%$; ischemic cardiomyopathy was present in 13. Six had a nonspecific interventricular conduction delay, and 29 fulfilled Strauss criteria for

TABLE 1 Clinical Characteristics of Patients	
Age, y	68 ± 8
Male	24 (69)
Comorbidities	
Coronary artery disease	13 (37)
Diabetes mellitus	13 (37)
Hypertension	29 (83)
LV ejection fraction, %	29 ± 6
LVEDD, mm	63 ± 6
QRS morphology	
LBBB	29 (83)
NIVCD	6 (17)
QRSd, ms	168 ± 24
Lead V ₆ RWPT during LVSP, ms	91 ± 17
Lead V ₆ RWPT during LBBP, ms	81 ± 14
q-LV of CS lead used for BVP, ms	131 ± 25
Values are mean ± SD or n (%).	
BVP = biventricular pacing; CS = coronary sinus; LBBB = left bundle branch block; LBBP = left bundle branch pacing; LV = left ventricular; LVEDD = left ventricular end-diastolic diameter; LVSP = left ventricular septal myocardial pacing; NIVCD = nonspecific intraventricular conduction delay; q-LV = distance from the beginning of the QRS complex to the maximum negative derivative of unipolar electrogram of coronary sinus lead electrode; QRSd = QRS duration; RWPT = R-wave peak time.	

LBBB. The average intrinsic QRSd was 168 ± 24 ms (Table 1).

At least 1 type of left septal pacing and successful RVASP were achieved in 34 patients (17 by LVSP and 25 by LBBP). BVP was successfully achieved in 31 patients; in 2 patients, CS cannulation was unsuccessful; and in 2 others, no suitable CS branch was present. At least 2 CRT captures were obtained in 31 patients, and in 8 patients, all 3 CRT pacing types were achieved during the implantation procedure. UHF electrocardiographic data were successfully obtained during all ventricular captures in all patients. No periprocedural complication occurred.

BVP, LVSP, and LBBP significantly reduced QRSd compared with RVASP (−46 ms [95% CI: −55 to −37 ms] during BVP, −45 ms [95% CI: −55 to −36 ms] during LBBP, and −45 ms [95% CI: −56 to −34 ms] during LVSP; $P < 0.001$ for all). However, there was no statistical difference in QRSd among them. These pacing strategies also significantly reduced global ventricular electrical dyssynchrony compared with RVASP; however, LBBP was associated with greater LV-to-right ventricular dyssynchrony than BVP (the mean difference in global ventricular electrical dyssynchrony was −24 ms [95% CI: −36 to −11 ms]; $P < 0.001$). Global ventricular electrical dyssynchrony during LVSP was the same as during BVP (mean difference −8 ms [95% CI: −22 to 6 ms]; $P = 0.30$). In contrast, LBBP produced shorter LV electrical

TABLE 2 Summary of Parameters of Ventricular Electrical Dyssynchrony and Systolic Blood Pressure During Studied Ventricular Captures				
Type of Capture	Paced QRSd, ms	e-DYS, ms	lv-DYS, ms	Systolic BP, mm Hg
BVP	156 ± 29	4 ± 29	25 ± 9	124 ± 18
LVSP	156 ± 18	−4 ± 26	19 ± 13	127 ± 14
LBBP	156 ± 16	−20 ± 24	18 ± 9	126 ± 20
RVASP	200 ± 28	62 ± 18	61 ± 19	116 ± 17
Values are mean ± SD.				
BP = blood pressure; e-DYS = global electrical ventricular dyssynchrony; lv-DYS = left ventricular electrical dyssynchrony; RVASP = right ventricular apicoseptal pacing; other abbreviations as in Table 1.				

dyssynchrony (−10 ms [95% CI: −16 to −4 ms]; $P = 0.001$), and local depolarization durations under leads V₄ to V₈ were shorter during LBBP than during BVP (Figure 2). There was no difference in LV electrical dyssynchrony between LVSP and BVP (−5 ms [95% CI: −12 to 1 ms]; $P = 0.10$), and local depolarization durations under leads V₅ to V₈ were the same.

In the hemodynamic study, we analyzed 12,928 systolic blood pressure values, of which 4,032 were during BVP, 2,176 during LVSP, 2,624 during nonselective LBBP, and 4,096 during right ventricular apical pacing. Systolic blood pressure comparisons were successfully performed during 26 BVP vs RVASP, 17 LVSP vs RVASP, 21 LBBP vs RVASP, 17 LVSP vs BVP, and 20 LBBP vs BVP.

BVP, LVSP, and LBBP significantly increased systolic blood pressure compared with RVASP, with relative increases of 7% (95% CI: 6%-8%; $P < 0.001$) during BVP, 7% (95% CI: 5%-9%; $P < 0.001$) during LVSP, and 11% (95% CI: 8%-13%; $P < 0.001$) during LBBP (Figure 3).

LBBP led to significantly higher systolic blood pressures than BVP (relative increase of 4% [95% CI: 2%-5%]; $P < 0.001$). There was no difference in systolic blood pressure between LVSP and BVP (1% [95% CI: 0%-2%]; $P = 0.10$) (Figures 4A and 4B). LBBP was associated with higher systolic blood pressure than BVP in 18 of 20 patients, while LVSP was better than BVP in 11 of 17 patients.

A summary of parameters of ventricular electrical dyssynchrony and systolic blood pressure during studied ventricular captures is provided in Table 2.

There were 8 patients in whom both LBBP and LVSP were successfully performed, and their hemodynamic parameters were compared with BVP during the implantation procedure. All of them had LBBB, and 4 had ischemic cardiomyopathy. The average lead depths were in these patients during LVSP shallower by 2 mm (95% CI: 1-3 mm; $P < 0.001$), lead

CENTRAL ILLUSTRATION BVP, LVSP, and LBBP Lead to LV Resynchronization Compared With RVASP. Better LV Synchrony During LBBP Translates to Higher Systolic Blood Pressure Increase Than During LVSP Compared With BVP

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BP = blood pressure; BVP = biventricular pacing; CRT = cardiac resynchronization therapy; LBBP = left bundle branch pacing; LV = left ventricular; LVSP = left ventricular septal myocardial pacing; RV = right ventricular; RVASP = right ventricular apico-septal pacing.

V₆ R-wave peak time was longer by 11 ms (95% CI: 3-18 ms; $P = 0.02$), and the amplitude of the current of injury was higher by 6 mV (95% CI: 3-8 mV; $P < 0.001$), compared with LBBP. Also, in these 8 patients, LBBP outperformed BVP (mean difference in systolic blood pressure 3% [95% CI: 2%-5%]; $P < 0.001$), and there was no difference between LVSP and BVP (mean difference 1% [95% CI: 0%-3%]; $P = 0.20$) (Figures 4C and 4D).

Comparing hemodynamic status in 22 patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy and 13 with ischemic cardiomyopathy showed that in both groups, BVP and LVSP led to the same relative increase in systolic blood pressure compared with RVASP (in both groups, 7% during BVP and 7% during LVSP; $P < 0.001$ for all comparisons). The effect of LBBP over RVASP was greater in patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy than in those with ischemic cardiomyopathy (11% vs 9%; $P < 0.001$ for both) (Supplemental Figure 1). Also, the increase in systolic blood

pressure during LBBP vs BVP was higher in patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy ($n = 13$) (relative increase 5% [95% CI: 3%-7%]; $P < 0.001$) than those with ischemic cardiomyopathy ($n = 7$) (relative increase 2% [95% CI: 0%-4%]; $P = 0.08$) (Figure 5). The difference in systolic blood pressure between LVSP and BVP in 9 patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy was not statistically different (2% [95% CI: 0%-4%]; $P = 0.06$) but was greater than in 8 patients with ischemic cardiomyopathy, in whom blood pressure during LVSP vs BVP was the same (0% [95% CI: -1% to 1%]; $P = 0.99$).

DISCUSSION

In this study, we compared 2 novel methods for delivering CRT, LBBP and LV septal pacing, with the established method of BVP. We found by using UHF ECG that LBBP delivered more synchronous LV activation, which translated into greater improvements

in acute hemodynamic function compared with BVP. In contrast, we did not observe any difference in LV electrical synchrony and hemodynamic status between LVSP and BVP. Finally, the study shows that the hemodynamic effects of LBBP and LVSP vs BVP may depend on the etiology of heart failure, with a greater benefit observed in patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy.

DIFFERENCES IN VENTRICULAR ACTIVATION BETWEEN LVSP, LBBP, AND BVP IN CRT PATIENTS. LVSP and LBBP are relatively new CRT methods, which provide ventricular resynchronization by capturing directly the LBB fibers and/or myocytes near the LBB. Both LBBP and LVSP result in a similarly paced QRS configuration, with a pseudo-right bundle branch configuration, indicating delayed right ventricular activation and the same QRSD.⁶ We have already demonstrated in patients with bradycardia that LBBP and LVSP are both less physiological than His bundle pacing and that LVSP provides a worse LV activation pattern than LBBP, which, in contrast, is associated with greater interventricular dyssynchrony than LVSP.⁶ In this study, we investigated how these differences in electrical synchrony translate into LV myocardial work effectivity in patients with CRT indications. We demonstrated that the QRSD is an unreliable marker of LV resynchronization, as it did not differ among LVSP, LBBP, and BVP. However, LBBP led to better LV synchrony and higher systolic blood pressure compared with BVP, despite greater left-to-right electrical dyssynchrony. LVSP and BVP had the same UHF electrocardiographic ventricular activation pattern and LV synchrony, and no difference in systolic blood pressure was observed between them (**Central Illustration**). It is important to emphasize that none of the LVSPs in the recent work were obtained by decreasing the pacing output from LBBP, and in pacing locations that provided LVSP, LBB capture was impossible even with pacing outputs up to 10 V at 0.5 ms. The effect of LVSP in close proximity to the LBB (ie, those LVSPs that transitioned from LBBP during the decremental output pacing) in the CRT population needs to be further investigated, as we previously showed that in patients with bradycardia, LVSP in close proximity to the LBB does not differ from LBBP in terms of electrical ventricular dyssynchrony.⁸

LV HEMODYNAMIC STATUS DURING LBBP, LVSP, AND BVP AND THE INFLUENCE OF HEART FAILURE ETIOLOGY. The aim of CRT is to decrease electromechanical ventricular dyssynchrony and to improve LV function in patients with heart failure.¹¹ We have shown that all 3 CRT methods significantly improved

LV hemodynamic status compared with RVASP, and although LBBP was shown to be superior to BVP, there was no difference in hemodynamic status between LVSP and BVP. Studies on the CRT effect of LBBP and LVSP vs BVP in a population of CRT recipients with both ischemic and nonischemic cardiomyopathy are few. However, it has been shown that in a dominantly nonischemic population, LBBP outperforms BVP relative to electrical and mechanical resynchronization, hemodynamic status, and LV ejection fraction improvement. Liang et al¹ showed that LV mechanical synchrony and dp/dt_{max} were better during LBBP than during BVP. They observed a relative difference in dp/dt_{max} of 4% in favor of LBBP, which is the same magnitude of difference we saw for systolic blood pressures in our study. Ali et al¹² showed that His bundle pacing and LBB area pacing were associated with a greater reduction in LV activation time (measured using electrocardiographic imaging) than BVP. LBB area pacing produced an incremental increase of systolic blood pressure of about 40% over BVP compared with baseline rhythm; we observed an additional 36% increase in blood pressure for LBBP over BVP compared with baseline RVASP. Finally, in a randomized trial comparing LBBP vs BVP in patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy and Strauss-defined LBBB, LBBP was associated with significantly more LV ejection fraction improvement and a decline in N-terminal pro-brain natriuretic peptide than BVP.² These data show that in patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy and LBBB, LBBP provides more synchronous electromechanical LV activation and more efficient LV function, which results in greater LV ejection fraction improvement than BVP. However, LBBP is not a straightforward procedure. In many cases, direct LBB capture cannot be achieved, and in these patients, LVSP is a common procedural outcome. The only data on the difference between LVSP vs BVP on ventricular resynchronization and hemodynamic status is the work of Salden et al,³ who performed LVSP using a catheter placed at the LV septum with a retrograde transaortic approach. They showed that LVSP provides greater electrical resynchronization (in terms of QRS area and reduction in the standard deviation of activation times), but the hemodynamic improvement during LVSP was similar to that obtained with BVP. They included 27 patients, of whom 44% had ischemic cardiomyopathy, but they did not report their results separately.

Our data indicate that the etiology of heart failure may be an important factor influencing LV hemodynamic status during LBBP compared with BVP. In patients with nonischemic myopathy, the systolic

blood pressure difference between LBBP and BVP was 2.9% higher compared with that in patients with ischemic cardiomyopathy. The efficacy of LBBP assumes synchronous LV activation via an intact conduction system in patients with proximal conduction disease. Thus, the resulting effect depends on the location and extent of LV conduction disease. In contrast, during BVP, which relies on myocardial cell-to-cell conduction, conduction properties of the LV myocardium, rather than the conductive tissue, may be more important.¹³ For these reasons, patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy, in which a proximal LBBB is more commonly present, may benefit more from LBBP than from BVP. In patients with ischemic cardiomyopathy, the effect of any CRT method will depend on the patient-specific combination of location and extent of LV conduction and myocardial disease.

STUDY LIMITATIONS. First, BVP could not be performed in all patients, because of either an inability to access the CS or unsuitable branches for LV pacing. In contrast, having only optimal positioning of pacing leads during BVP, we tried not to handicap BVP against LBBP and LVSP. Although we used strict criteria for LBBP, we cannot exclude that in some patients, LVSP was in fact LBBP due to LV conduction tissue and myocardium having equal capture thresholds. To distinguish between them would require mapping of the LV aspect of the interventricular septum, which was not done in the study. In contrast, the same hemodynamic effects were seen in 8 patients in whom both LVSP and LBBP were detected during the same implantation procedure. For this reason, we believe that our results represent the real effects of LVSP and LBBP on ventricular synchrony and LV hemodynamic status in CRT patients. On the basis of clinical presentation and coronary angiography, the patients were classified as having ischemic or nonischemic cardiomyopathy. It would be more valuable to know the location and extent of scars or other LV pathologies, which may be responsible for differences in LV activation and contraction during various CRT methods. However, in our study, cardiac magnetic resonance imaging was used infrequently. Finally, the number of patients and types of ventricular captures included and in the study were limited.

CONCLUSIONS

UHF ECG allowed us to document differences in LV synchrony among LBBP, LVSP, and BVP that were not

observed by measuring QRSd. In addition, our results show that the level of UHF electrocardiographic LV synchrony translates into better LV performance. All 3 strategies—BVP, LVSP, and LBBP—improved the deteriorated LV hemodynamic status caused by dyssynchronous ventricular activation during RVASP. LVSP and LBBP may serve as alternative CRT methods that provide the same or better LV synchrony and hemodynamic status compared with BVP, with a potentially greater benefit observed in patients with nonischemic cardiomyopathy. Whether these effects of LVSP and LBBP translate into better clinical outcomes needs to be validated in prospective clinical trials.

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PERSPECTIVES

COMPETENCY IN MEDICAL KNOWLEDGE: UHF ECG assesses the differences in LV electrical synchrony among BVP, LVSP, and LBBP better than QRSd. In addition to BVP, both LVSP and LBBP may be used as alternative methods of resynchronization therapy with a similar or improved LV synchrony and performance.

TRANSLATIONAL OUTLOOK: Further research is needed to determine whether, in patients with heart failure and dyssynchronous ventricular activation, LVSP and LBBP are associated with similar or better clinical outcomes compared with BVP.

REFERENCES

1. Liang Y, Wang J, Gong X, et al. Left bundle branch pacing versus biventricular pacing for acute cardiac resynchronization in patients with heart failure. *Circ Arrhythm Electrophysiol*. 2022;15(11):e011181.
2. Wang Y, Zhu H, Hou X, et al. Randomized trial of left bundle branch vs biventricular pacing for cardiac resynchronization therapy. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2022;80(13):1205-1216.
3. Salden F, Luermans J, Westra SW, et al. Short-term hemodynamic and electrophysiological effects of cardiac resynchronization by left ventricular septal pacing. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2020;75(4):347-359.
4. Jurak P, Curila K, Leinveber P, et al. Novel ultra-high-frequency electrocardiogram tool for the description of the ventricular depolarization pattern before and during cardiac resynchronization. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol*. 2020;31(1):300-307.
5. Curila K, Jurak P, Halamek J, et al. Ventricular activation pattern assessment during right ventricular pacing: ultrahigh-frequency ECG study. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol*. 2021;32(5):1385-1394.
6. Curila K, Jurak P, Jastrzebski M, et al. Left bundle branch pacing compared to left ventricular septal myocardial pacing increases interventricular dyssynchrony but accelerates left ventricular lateral wall depolarization. *Heart Rhythm*. 2021;18(8):1281-1289.
7. Curila K, Prochazkova R, Jurak P, et al. Both selective and nonselective His bundle, but not myocardial, pacing preserve ventricular electrical synchrony assessed by ultra-high-frequency ECG. *Heart Rhythm*. 2020;17(4):607-614.
8. Curila K, Jurak P, Vernooy K, et al. Left ventricular myocardial septal pacing in close proximity to LBB does not prolong the duration of the left ventricular lateral wall depolarization compared to LBB pacing. *Front Cardiovasc Med*. 2021;8:787414.
9. Huang W, Chen X, Su L, et al. A beginner's guide to permanent left bundle branch pacing. *Heart Rhythm*. 2019;16(12):1791-1796.
10. Shun-Shin MJ, Miyazawa AA, Keene D, et al. How to deliver personalized cardiac resynchronization therapy through the precise measurement of the acute hemodynamic response: Insights from the iSpot trial. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol*. 2019;30(9):1610-1619.
11. Prinzen FW, Vernooy K, De Boeck BW, et al. Mechano-energetics of the asynchronous and resynchronized heart. *Heart Fail Rev*. 2011;16(3):215-224.
12. Ali N, Arnold AD, Miyazawa AA, et al. Comparison of methods for delivering cardiac resynchronization therapy: an acute electrical and haemodynamic within-patient comparison of left bundle branch area, His bundle, and biventricular pacing. *Europace*. 2023;25(3):1060-1067.
13. Strocchi M, Gillette K, Neic A, et al. Effect of scar and His-Purkinje and myocardium conduction on response to conduction system pacing. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol*. 2023;34(4):984-993.

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APPENDIX For a supplemental figure, please see the online version of this paper.